

Metaphors of Emotions in English Discourse

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Abstract. The aim of this essay is to investigate what the relationship of emotions and metaphors in different expressions in English language using different language units. In emotion metaphors reveals about the connections between something utterly concrete, such as motion, and something very abstract, such as emotion.

Key words: *Emotions, metaphors, Constitutive metaphors, category, happiness, fear, sadness, anger.*

Introduction

Interrelation of the formal categories of language within the modes of thought of the person speaking them is in continuous disputes among the scholars of linguistics and psychology. It should not be omitted that the way of expressing emotion is mostly individual, taking into consideration the background or the status of the speaker. In many languages direct relations between the formal categories and cultural life and thought are extremely difficult to trace because of the extremely formal character of the linguistic categories we find. For this reason, the grouping of a particular body of phenomena in a given category may not necessarily be significant as an index of a people's view of the natural world. Nevertheless, most universal emotions such as happiness, fear, sadness, or anger still have some common grounds among cultures in expressing with similar linguistic devices such as metaphors or grammatical units.[4]

Methodology

Emotions, although they have a physical base, are not physical entities and therefore at the very least must be talked about in what Lakoff/ Johnson (1980) refer to as ontological metaphors. By conceptualizing emotions as substances or things through ontological metaphor, we can refer to them, identify their parts, causes, and effects, and handle them in other ways that would be impossible without such metaphors. So, we talk about, for example, the root of someone's dislike, the peak of frustration, or the Wellspring of happiness. Metaphors serve two basic functions in relation to emotion: They express emotions concretely, and they indirectly conjure up emotions in the hearer. To talk about emotions, to express our feelings, we use metaphors like "The loss out me to the quick".

Metaphor indirectly elicits emotion from hearers with specific words or phrases like cringing and robust. [2]

Lakoff/Johnson (1980) argue that most of our conceptual system is metaphorical in nature. They give numerous examples of how our ways of speaking and thinking are grounded on certain base metaphors. This is especially true of the expression of emotions, since emotions are not entities that we can point to in the physical world; there is no concrete referent for love, anger, hate, or other emotions, but only images like burning, seeing red, walking on clouds and so on. The importance of metaphor and the expression of emotions extends from the area of linguistics into the area of psychology. The expression of our emotions shapes and defines the initial sensation into a manageable concept. The expression - or repression - of emotion is an area Freud (1901) was concerned with; he explained that repressed emotions, not openly talked about, find outlets beyond the conscious control of those feeling them, in slips of the tongue, for instance, which let our hearers in on what we really feel. [3]

Self as a Container for Emotions

"I am full of anger."

"I am brimming over with rage."

"I am full of love."

"I feel empty inside."

Emotions as Containers

"I am in a state of despair."

"I am living in fear."

"I am in love."

"I am in a great frame of mind."

Emotions as Temperature

"That leaves me cold."

"I'm all hot and bothered."

"I am boiling with anger."

"She is an ice queen."

"I am cold-hearted."

Emotions as Pressure

"I am going to explode in a minute."

"He just erupted without warning."

"He's like a volcano about to explode."

"I need to let off steam."

"I'm under a lot of pressure." [6]

Discussion

Additionally, negative emotions are often referred to as forms of physical damage, such as, "I am hurt," "I am torn apart," "I feel suffocated," "I'm feeling crushed," and so on. An understanding of the metaphorical structure of emotions can lead to a rapid and profound change in both emotional health and relationships. In therapy, mismatching commonly occurs whereby the patient reports something like, "feeling crushed" and the therapist responds by trying to "put the client's life back together," which, of course, would be more apt for the client whose life has "fallen apart" or is "in pieces/in bits." [2]

Wierzbicka (1972) similarly concentrated on the initial event and our positive or negative judgment of it as the basis for distinctions in the vocabulary of emotions. [5]

There are some examples of metaphor and their systematic formation

Metaphor for

+ANGER-AS-BURDEN

ex. Donni carries his anger around with him.

+ANGER-AS-DANGEROUS-ANIMAL

ex. She unleashed his anger.

+ANGER-AS-FIRE

ex. What you said inflamed James.

+ANGER-AS-HOT-CONTAINED-FLUID

ex. You make my blood boil.

+ANGER-AS-OPPONENT

ex. She has been wrestling with her anger.

+ANGER-AS-STORM

ex. Tom thundered with rage.

Constitutive metaphors oppose both happy and sad, love and hate, but basic-level metaphors for the two work differently. Whereas most basic level metaphors for happy and sad are not closely related, standard basiclevel metaphors conceptualize both love and hate as extremes on scales from indifference to passion, and these in turn as parallel to scales for temperature from cold to hot, from weak to strong force, and from sanity to madness. So, we can be burning with love or hate, overpowered or crazy with either love or hate, and this also argues that the burden of understanding the emotions as distinct from one another must fall on constitutive metaphors, especially those involving judgments between desirable and undesirable states.

Metaphors have both direct emotional meaning and are integrated into our conceptual system, giving them a powerful emotional impact. According to Black's (1962) example, referring to AI as a wolf not only portrays him as a nasty animal, but also recalls culturally related commonplaces such as wolves being hostile, terrifying, and prone to attacking humans. The stereotype of the womanizer as a wolf carries negative implications. Metaphors have been researched for their emotional impact in linguistic art, but they are also used in politics and advertising to accomplish certain outcomes.[1]

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have demonstrated that metaphor and emotion are intricately intertwined. Metaphors help to express emotions and elicit emotional responses. We claimed that constitutive and basic-level metaphors have unique functions in terms of emotions. Basic-level metaphors are important to understand the sensory experience, whereas constitutive metaphors help distinguish emotions. Finally, we explored how metaphors can provoke emotions and shape our attitudes toward what they describe.

References

1. Black M. 1962, *Models and Metaphors*, Cornell University Press, Ithaca
2. Lakoff G./Johnson M. 1980, *Metaphors We Live By*, University of Chicago Press, Chicago
3. Freud S. 1901 (1960), *The Psychopathology of Everyday Life*, trans, by J.Strachey, Hogarth, London
4. Ubaydullayeva, D. (2024). EMOTIONS AS CONCEPTS IN COGNITIVE LINGUISTICS. *Science and innovation in the education system*, 3(4), 11-15.
5. Убайдуллаева, Д. (2024). Концептуализация термина «гнев» в английской лингвокультуре. *Зарубежная лингвистика и лингводидактика*, 2(1), 157-162.
6. Wierzbicka A. 1972, *Semantic Primitives*, Athenäum, Frankfurt/Main
7. <https://metaphorsofmovement.co.uk/metaphors-of-movement-and-motion/metaphors-of-emotion/>